

Landscape Analysis of PID Infrastructure and Awareness in Sub-Saharan Africa

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Table of Contents

Table of Contents	2
List of Table	4
Table of Figures	5
Glossary	6
Executive Summary	7
1. Introduction	8
1.1 Understanding Open Infrastructure and Open Science	8
1.2 The Role of PIDs in building a trusted research infrastructure	8
1.3 How DataCite is building a sustainable research infrastructure	10
1.5 Scope	10
2. Methodology	11
2.1 Design	11
2.2 Sources of Data	11
2.2.1 Sources of data for PIDs infrastructural analysis	11
2.2.2 Sources of data for PIDs awareness analysis	11
2.3 Data Analysis	12
2.3.1 Infrastructure landscape data analysis	12
2.3.2 PIDs awareness landscape analysis	12
3. Results and Discussions	13
3.1 Infrastructure Landscape Analysis of Sub-Saharan Africa	13
3.1.1 Existing repositories and systems in sub-Saharan Africa	14
3.1.1.1 Registry of Open Access Repositories (ROAR)	14
3.1.1.2 Directorate of Open Access Repositories (OpenDOAR)	15
3.1.1.3 Registry of Research Data Repositories (re3data)	16
3.1.1.4 Comparison of the number of repositories by source	17
3.1.2 Existing repositories and systems in sub-Saharan Africa	19
3.1.2.1 Registry of Open Access Repositories (ROAR)	19
3.1.2.2 Directorate of Open Access Repositories (OpenDOAR)	20
3.1.2.3 Other service providers in sub-Saharan Africa	21
3.1.3 PID Systems and Infrastructure Landscape in Sub-Saharan Africa	24
3.1.3.1 RE3DATA	24
3.1.3.2 DataCite DOI	25

3.2 Landscape Analysis of PIDs Awareness in Sub-Saharan Africa	26
3.2.1 Landscape of Open Science Policies in Sub-Saharan Africa	26
3.2.2 ROARMAP Open Access Policies	27
3.2.4 PIDs awareness landscape discussions	29
4. Conclusion	30
Reference	32
Funding Statement	33
Acknowledgments	34

List of Table

Table	Description	Page
3.1	Sub-regions and countries analyzed.	13

Table of Figures

Figure	Description	Page
3.1	Number of repositories per country from ROAR	15
3.2	Number of repositories in sub-Saharan Africa by country from OpenDOAR	16
3.3	Number of repositories by country in sub-Saharan Africa from re3data	17
3.4	Number of repositories in sub-Saharan Africa by source	18
3.5	Comparison of numbers of repositories in sub-Saharan Africa by country	19
3.6	Service Providers in sub-Saharan Africa Repositories from ROAR	20
3.7	Number of providers in sub-Saharan Africa by OpenDOAR	21
3.8	Dspace Installation in sub-Saharan Africa by Lyrisis	22
3.9	OJS Installation per country in sub-Saharan Africa	23
3.10	PID infrastructure by country in sub-Saharan Africa by re3data	25
3.11	DOI per country in sub-Saharan Africa	26
3.12	National open science policy in Africa	27
3.13	Number of open access policies per country	28
3.14	Open science policy adopted per quarter	29

Glossary

COAR	Confederation of Open Access Repositories
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
OJS	Open Journal System
OMP	Open Monograph Preprint
OpenDOAR	Directory of Open Access Repositories
OPS	Open Preprint System
PID	Persistent Identifier
PKP	Public Knowledge Project Usage Data
Re3data	Registry of Research Data Repositories
ROAR	Registry of Open Access Repositories
UNESCO	United Nations Education, Scientific and Cultural Organization

Executive Summary

Persistent identifiers (PIDs) play a crucial role in ensuring the longevity and accessibility of digital resources. In sub-Saharan Africa, the landscape regarding PIDs has been evolving to address various challenges related to research, data management, and access. This work focussed on analyzing the PID infrastructure and awareness in sub-Saharan Africa. DataCite observed a lower representation of some regions in their DOI infrastructure. Africa, as a region, is one of the observed regions with a lesser number of DOIs originating from the region as well as underlying repository infrastructure. The aim of the report is to have an understanding of the Open Science infrastructure in Sub-Saharan Africa and the objectives include:

- I. Review of existing works on PID infrastructure in the region
- II. Ascertain the level of PID infrastructure awareness in the region
- III. Identify the existing gaps and make suggestions to close these gaps.

This report covers a review of existing persistent identifiers for scholarly works, as well as the extent of awareness of these identifiers in sub-Saharan Africa. The data used in this landscape analysis were taken from several sources including ROAR, DOAR, Re3data, and UNESCO. The study observed the extent of PID infrastructure availability in the region using the data from trusted public sources and assessed PID awareness across different countries based on the available data. Although there are different types of PIDs such as ROR (Research Organization Registry) which is used to identify research institutions, and ORCID (Open Researcher and Contributor ID) which is used to identify individual researchers, this study focused mostly on DOIs, which are used to identify research outputs, and the state of the awareness in sub-Saharan Africa.

This report is relevant to multi-stakeholders in the open science ecosystem. It will be resourceful for policy makers to identify the gaps in their respective countries, provide improved visibility to funders on how to support and collaborate within the region on the institutionalization of open science and its infrastructure, serve as a source of further study for researchers, while partners and stakeholders in the open science ecosystems will have a baseline to provide the necessary support for the region.

1. Introduction

1.1 Understanding Open Infrastructure and Open Science

The European Organization for Nuclear Research (CERN) defines Open Infrastructure as the set of technological tools and services that support and enable open science practices. Grand *et al.* (2012) defined open science as an emerging approach to the conduct of science, technology, and engineering projects, in which information about the whole of an ongoing investigation is made available on and through the internet. The two definitions could imply the dependence of open science practices on open infrastructure. Open infrastructure requires technological tools and services which should be readily accessible through and on the internet. For resources to be available on the internet, these must be hosted on a webserver with a persistent internet address.

Open infrastructure, as an open science enabler, has some features that makes it a trusted source. [The Principles of Open Scholarly Infrastructure \(POSI\)](#), a set of principles which ensure the openness, sustainability and accountability of key infrastructure that supports open scholarly communication address all the elements that makes open infrastructure trusted. With three core themes, POSI provides the framework that ensures the governance, sustainability and insurance of open infrastructure. Governance, in POSI, addresses inclusive community governance with a clear and transparent decision making process. Sustainability provides a clear long term sustainability plan beyond dependence on a single source of funding while Insurance involves the implementation of policies to ensure long term preservation of the infrastructure and data even in the case of organization change or dissolution.

1.2 The Role of PIDs in building a trusted research infrastructure

To enable FAIR research, every research output in open science is expected to have a unique and persistent digital identifier. In the case of DOIs, this identifier is created within the open infrastructure (the repository) by working with Registration Agencies (RA) platform(s). The unique identifier otherwise known as persistent identifiers (PIDs) help to identify each research output within an open infrastructure. PIDs could be for different purposes. The purpose also depends on the richness of the metadata schema, including the connectedness and interoperability, behind the PID infrastructure as well as the completeness of the metadata entered by the person uploading such research output.

PIDs contribute to research outputs accessibility and preservation. Implementing a robust PID system will enhance the discoverability, accessibility, re-use and citation of African research, thereby increasing its visibility globally.

PIDs provide the mechanism to determine the authenticity of any research output. By providing a permanent digital identity linked to rich metadata, including authorship, publication details, and provenance which enable traceability. PIDs are immutable, and changes made on metadata are trackable to ensure accountability or audit. PIDs and its associated metadata provide vital information about the research carried out, the research output, the person(s) involved in the research, the organization affiliation(s) of the individuals and their attributes. Persistent identifiers are well linked through the metadata records uploaded along with the research output into an open repository. This ensures that the associated research output retains the identity and attributes of persons and organizations with the research output.

PIDs promote trust for open infrastructures. PIDs and their associated metadata ensure that the information about the research output being accessed is readily available for secondary users. Information such as title, publication year, author, co-author, contributor(s), created date, version, relatedIdentifier and the digital object identifier for the research output are some of the metadata records that DOI provides. The metadata records could be used by citation formatter to provide ready to use citation for research outputs. So, the integration of PIDs into open infrastructure is necessary to ensure trust for the infrastructure, the research, the researcher and the institution. Additionally, PIDs enhance the visibility of the research infrastructure and promote attributions.

PIDs can also form the basis to develop research metrics. They can be used to measure the impact of research outputs using a number of elements. The number of clicks on DOI can be an indication of the number of users accessing a research output. A measurement of the views of DOI could indicate the number of interests in a particular research output. DOI could also track the downloads per DOI which could also indicate the reuse of the research output beyond the citations. In terms of citations, DOI removes errors in referencing by ensuring that citations are rightly attributed. The elimination of such error enhances citation measurement. This makes research outputs that use DOI to have improved visibility. This argument is noted in the work of Colavizza et al. (2020) where they observed that articles with DOIs experienced a 25.36% relative gain in citation counts which is an indication of values DOIs could bring to research outputs.

1.3 How DataCite is building a sustainable research infrastructure

DataCite is a global community that shares a common interest: to ensure that research outputs and resources are openly available and connected so that their reuse can advance knowledge across and between disciplines, now and in the future. As an organization, DataCite provides services to support open infrastructure and research connectedness with digital object identifier (DOI) metadata, APIs, integration services among others. Since the organization is governed by the member community, DataCite will continue to exist to provide the required persistent identifier infrastructure to support the community continuously.

In 2023, DataCite launched a Global Access program (GAP), an initiative to improve access and enable communities in lesser-represented regions to further benefit from DataCite's open infrastructure services. The initiative is made available through the support of CZI (Chan Zuckerberg Initiative). The Global Access Program (GAP) has 3 objectives: first, to collaborate with local communities and organizations on opportunities to improve awareness about open infrastructure (persistent identifiers and metadata) in different regions and languages; second, to support local communities in developing and adopting the necessary infrastructure to integrate persistent identifiers (PIDs) into their workflows according to their needs and opportunities, and third, to lower the barriers to accessing PID infrastructure by establishing a [Global Access Fund](#) that enables organizations to set up the infrastructure and adopt DOI registration services. This report is part of this initiative.

1.5 Scope

The scope of this report is limited to documented and publicly available open infrastructure in sub-Saharan Africa as well as evidence-based awareness about PIDs in the region. This work focuses on Sub-Saharan Africa and excludes the Arab speaking countries in Africa.

2. Methodology

2.1 Design

Creating a baseline for further study was considered in the design of this work. This includes the collection of existing data from trusted and credible public domains. The design compared the data collected from these sources using basic statistical methodologies and the use of charts. The design focused on the quantitative output of the secondary data sources. A total of 50 countries were identified within sub-Saharan Africa as a region. The countries were grouped as sub-regions. The count of various elements of an open science infrastructure for each country based on the source, were used in the analysis.

2.2 Sources of Data

2.2.1 Sources of data for PIDs infrastructural analysis

For the PIDs infrastructural data, the following data sources were accessed:

- I. [Directory of Open Access Repositories \(OpenDOAR\)](#),
- II. [Registry of Open Access Repositories \(ROAR\)](#),
- III. [Registry of Research Data Repositories \(re3data\)](#)
- IV. [Public Knowledge Project Usage Data \(PKP\)](#)
- V. [Dataverse Installations Data](#)
- VI. [Dspace Installations Data](#)
- VII. [DataCite Commons](#)

2.2.2 Sources of data for PIDs awareness analysis

For PIDs awareness data, a few existing sources were found for sub-Saharan Africa. These includes:

- I. [UNESCO](#)
- II. [Registry of Open Access Repositories MAP \(ROARMAP\)](#)
- III. [DataCite Commons](#)

2.3 Data Analysis

Quantitative statistical data analysis using median, mean and mode was adopted for the work. Qualitative data analysis was also used to show the degree of certain indicators in the study based on the data collected. Comparative analysis of the various data sources was carried out and inferences were drawn from the available data.

2.3.1 Infrastructure landscape data analysis

The infrastructure landscape analysis follows the original design methodology. Data collected from multiple sources were curated separately as tabular datasets. Data collected including the respective countries with the count of DOIs created by country (where available), the number of repository software (also called providers), Subsequently, the curated data were converted to charts for visualization. Central tendencies statistical analysis methodology was used from the charts to determine the mode and the median. In some cases, especially when considering the type of software used by each infrastructure, we were determined to get a reliable central tendency analysis. Additionally, qualitative statistical data analysis was used to identify patterns in the charts.

2.3.2 PIDs awareness landscape analysis

The degree of awareness about PIDs in sub-Saharan Africa was analyzed using both qualitative and quantitative data analysis methodologies. The study focused on the countries which makes the data analysis consistent with qualitative data analysis methodology. Patterns were drawn from the curated data for tables and charts. Majorly, the establishment or presence of an open science policy in each country was used as a means to measure the degree of the awareness of open science in each country.

3. Results and Discussions

3.1 Infrastructure Landscape Analysis of Sub-Saharan Africa

The 50 countries covered in the study are in Table 3.1 . The results of the existing open science repositories and PIDs infrastructure data collected were discussed

Table 3.1 Sub-regions and countries analyzed.

Subregion	Country / Territory
Eastern Africa	Burundi
	Comoros
	Djibouti
	Eritrea
	Ethiopia
	Kenya
	Madagascar
	Malawi
	Mauritius
	Mozambique
	Rwanda
	Seychelles
	Somalia
	Somaliland
	South Sudan
	Tanzania
	Uganda
Zambia	
Zimbabwe	
Central Africa	Angola
	Cameroon
	Central African Republic
	Chad
	Congo, Democratic Republic of the
	Congo, Republic of the
	Equatorial Guinea
	Gabon

	São Tomé and Príncipe
Southern Africa	Botswana
	Eswatini (Swaziland)
	Lesotho
	Namibia
	South Africa
Western Africa	Benin
	Burkina Faso
	Cape Verde
	Chad
	Côte d'Ivoire (Ivory Coast)
	Gambia, The
	Ghana
	Guinea
	Guinea-Bissau
	Liberia
	Mali
	Mauritania
	Niger
	Nigeria
	Senegal
Sierra Leone	
Togo	

3.1.1 Existing repositories and systems in sub-Saharan Africa

There are a number of repositories in sub-Saharan Africa. Different sources have different records. The records from each source considers the available repositories in each country.

3.1.1.1 Registry of Open Access Repositories (ROAR)

In the records from the Registry of Open Access Repositories (ROAR), a total of 157 repositories were accounted for. Out of this 157, South Africa has the highest number of repositories with 53 followed by Kenya with 32 before a distant third by Nigeria with 17 and Zimbabwe with 12. Other countries with records of repositories in ROAR include Tanzania and Uganda with each country having 9 repositories while Ghana has 6, Botswana has 4, and Ethiopia has 3. Senegal, Namibia and Lesotho have 2 repositories each while Cameroon, Somalia and Malawi have one repository each. Other countries in the region do

not have any record of existing repositories, based on data from ROAR. A total of 17 countries were recorded having at least a repository, representing about 35% of the countries in sub-Saharan Africa (See Figure 3.1).

Figure 3.1 Number of repositories per country from [ROAR](#)
 Source: [Registry of Open Access Repositories \(ROAR\)](#). Access: September 2023

3.1.1.2 Directorate of Open Access Repositories (OpenDOAR)

According to the Directorate of Open Access Repositories (OpenDOAR), 212 repositories were identified. As observed in the data taken from ROAR, the trend, in terms of ranking, is closely related for the first 3 countries though with different numbers of repositories recorded. South Africa has the highest number of repositories recorded by OpenDOAR with 51 accounted for followed by Kenya with 46 and Nigeria with 31. Tanzania, Uganda and Zimbabwe have 17, 15 and 11 respectively while Ghana, Ethiopia, Botswana, Senegal, Malawi and Zambia have 9, 6, 4, 4, 3 and 3 respectively. Cape Verde, Namibia, Lesotho, Mozambique and Rwanda recorded 2 each while Cameroon and Somalia have 1 each. The remaining countries have no record of visible repositories. OpenROAR accounted for 18 countries in the region, representing about 36% of the total. (See Figure 3.2)

Number of Repositories Per Country. source - OpenDOAR

Figure 3.2 Number of repositories in sub-Saharan Africa by country from [OpenDOAR](#)
 Source: [Directorate of Open Access Repositories \(OpenDOAR\)](#) Access: September 2023

3.1.1.3 Registry of Research Data Repositories (re3data)

The Registry of Research Data Repositories (re3data) listed 37 repositories. Except for South Africa and Kenya with 17 and 6 available repositories, others are not in line with the previous discussed sources. Burkina Faso has 3 while Ghana has 2 while Cameroon, Côte d’Ivoire, Benin, Namibia, Malawi, Nigeria, Niger, Senegal and Ethiopia have 1 repository each. There is no record of repositories for 37 countries. (See Figure 3.3)

Number of Repositories by Country/Territory in Sub-Saharan Africa. Data Source - RE3DATA

Figure 3.3 Number of repositories by country in sub-Saharan Africa from [re3data](https://re3data.org)
 Source: [Registry of Research Data Repositories, \(re3data\)](https://re3data.org). Access: September 2023

3.1.1.4 Comparison of the number of repositories by source

The largest number of repositories in sub-Saharan Africa was recorded by OpenDOAR, representing 52.3% when data from OpenDOAR, ROAR and re3data were combined. This is followed by ROAR with 38.7% while re3data is 9.1%. The difference between the data from re3data compared to both OpenDOAR and ROAR may be connected to the fact that re3data considers data repositories only, while OpenDOAR and DOAR consider all open science repositories. (See Figure 3.4)

Number of repositories by source

Figure 3.4 Number of repositories in sub-Saharan Africa by source
 Source: [Open DOAR](#), [ROAR](#) and [Re3Data](#). Access: September 2023

When drilling down into the number of repositories listed for each country by the three sources, Open DOAR, ROAR and re3data shows some similar pattern in the values registered for each country. South Africa was observed to have the highest number of repositories regardless of the source of the data while both Kenya and Nigeria follow respectively. South Africa recorded 51, 53 and 17 by OpenDOAR, ROAR and re3data respectively, Kenya recorded 46,32 and 6 by OpenDOAR, ROAR and re3data respectively while Nigeria recorded 31, 17 and 1 respectively by OpenDOAR, ROAR and re3data respectively. Apart from the prominent 3 countries, the number of repositories recorded for other countries also have a close trend based on the total number of repositories recorded by each source. This can be observed with Botswana, Ethiopia, Zimbabwe, Tanzania, Uganda, Namibia, Senegal, Lesotho, Cape Verde and Cameroon. Some countries were noted not to have any record or form of available open science repositories based on the data collected from the 3 sources. (See Figure 3.5)

Comparison of Available Repositories in Sub-Saharan Africa - OpenDOAR, ROAR and Re3data

Figure 3.5 Comparison of numbers of repositories in sub-Saharan Africa by country
 Source: [Open DOAR](#), [ROAR](#) and [Re3Data](#) . Access: September 2023

3.1.2 Existing repositories and systems in sub-Saharan Africa

Different repository software providers were observed across the region.

3.1.2.1 Registry of Open Access Repositories (ROAR)

Using the data collected from ROAR as shown in Figure 3.6, more than three-quarter of the repositories in the region use Dspace (121 installations). Others include Invenio (1.9%), ePrint (5.7%), Bepress (1.9%), ETD db (1.3%), Digitool (0.9%), Fedora (0.6%), others (5.3%).

Number of Providers in Sub-Saharan Africa. Source - OpenDOAR

Figure 3.7 Number of providers in sub-Saharan Africa by [OpenDOAR](#)
 Source: [Directory of Open Access Repositories \(OpenDOAR\)](#). Accessed: September 2023

3.1.2.3 Other service providers in sub-Saharan Africa

Other sources in this study include Dspace, Dataverse and Public Knowledge Project Usage Data (PKP). From Figure 3.8, a total of 205 Dspace installations was recorded on the [Dspace provider's website](#) with Kenya leading with 31 instances, South Africa with 30

instances, Niger with 29 and Nigeria with 28 instances.

Dspace installations Per Country. Source Lyrasis

Figure 3.8 Dspace Installation in sub-Saharan Africa by [Lyrasis](#)

Source: [Lyrasis](#). Access: September 2023

Unlike Dspace, only 2 instances of Dataverse were found on [the Dataverse website](#). Kenya has 1 as well as Botswana.

Public Knowledge Project Usage Data (PKP) has 3 types of software. OJS has the highest installations in the region. Among these, Nigeria has the largest number of installations with 218, South Africa has 123 and Kenya has 100. Ethiopia has 26, Ghana (20), Tanzania (15), Zambia (14) while Angola has 12. Others with units of installations include: Mozambique (7), Ugandan (6) while Botswana, Zimbabwe, Mali and DRC have 4 units each. Gambia has 3 while Congo, Cameroon, Rwanda, Senegal and Mauritania have 2 each. Benin, Burkina Faso, Burundi, Eswani, Guinea, Ivory Coast and Sierra Leone each have a unit. (See Figure 3.9)

Number of Journals in Sub-Saharan Africa Per Country. Source - OJS

Figure 3.9 OJS Installation per country in sub-Saharan Africa
Source: [Public Knowledge Project Usage Data \(PKP\)](#). Access: September 2023

Only 3 countries have Open Preprint system (OPS) installations. South Africa has 3 instances while Ethiopia and Nigeria has a unit instance each.

The Open Monograph Press system (OMP) has 3 countries in the region using it. South Africa has 7 instances, Zimbabwe has 3 instances while Congo has just a unit instance.

3.1.3 PID Systems and Infrastructure Landscape in Sub-Saharan Africa

Not all the sources of data provided the type of persistent identifier (PID) infrastructure and/or systems in the repositories identified in this work.

3.1.3.1 RE3DATA

From re3data, which focuses on data repositories, 3 major groups of PIDs were identified. These are DOI, Handle and others. DOI has the highest number (17) among the three followed by Others (13) and Handle (5). Lesotho has the highest number of PIDs with a total of 16 out of the 35 numbers identified in the region followed by Kenya with 5, Côte d'Ivoire, Malawi, Namibia and South Africa each with 2 while Niger, Mauritania, Mali, Burkina Faso, Ethiopia and Angola each with 1. (See Figure 3.10).

Number of PIDs Type in Sub-Saharan Africa. Source - Re3data

Figure 3.10 PIDs infrastructure by country in sub-Saharan Africa by [re3data](#)
 Source: [Registry of Research Data Repositories, \(re3data\)](#). Access: September 2023

3.1.3.2 DataCite DOI

As at the time of this work, there are about 150,000 DOI from the region with more than a third coming from South Africa, over 20,000 from Ethiopia, Nigeria with a little over 3,000, Kenya with about 3,000, Cote d'Ivoire with about a thousand and Malawi just below a thousand.

DOI Per Country in Sub-Saharan Africa. Source - DataCite

Figure 3.14 DOI per country in sub-Saharan Africa

Source: [DataCite's Commons](#). Accessed: September 2023

3.2 Landscape Analysis of PID Awareness in Sub-Saharan Africa

Some factors were considered as important elements to provide insight into the landscape of PIDs awareness in sub-Saharan Africa. Availability of policy that institutionalized PIDs as well as DataCite's membership provided insight to the degree of PIDs awareness in the region.

3.2.1 Landscape of Open Science Policies in Sub-Saharan Africa

From the data available from UNESCO, only South Africa and Ethiopia, have active national open science policy while Mozambique, Somalia, Tanzania, Uganda, Lesotho, Côte d'Ivoire, Ghana and Nigeria were under preparation at the time of the report available from UNESCO. Other African countries had no record of either availability or preparation for a national open science policy. (See Figure 3.12)

Figure 3.12 National open science policy in Africa

Source: [UNESCO](https://www.unesco.org/en/roarmap). Access: September 2023

3.2.2 ROARMAP Open Access Policies

Out of the 33 policies identified in the region by the Registry of Open Access Repositories Mandatory Archiving Policies (ROARMAP), Kenya has 16, South Africa has 11, Zimbabwe 2 while Ghana, Nigeria, Tanzania, and Burundi each has 1. (See Figure 3.13)

Number of Policies Per Country/Territory. Source - ROARMAP

Figure 3.13 Number of open access policies per country

Source: [Registry of Open Access Repositories Mandatory Archiving Policies \(ROARMAP\)](#). Accessed: September 2023

In terms of the frequency of policy creation, the region started experiencing growth in the number from 2011 steadily while 2019 has a plateau until Q3 of 2019. (See Figure 3.14)

Figure 3.14 Open science policy adopted per quarter

Source: [Registry of Open Access Repositories Mandatory Archiving Policies \(ROARMAP\)](#). Accessed: September 2023

3.2.4 PIDs awareness landscape discussion

The landscape of PIDs awareness landscape is still nascent and growing in the region. The result from the UNESCO data on national open science policy indicated that few countries in the region are preparing to adopt national open science policy in addition to the existing 2 countries identified. The awareness level, though low, is promising.

4. Conclusion

This landscape analysis provides an overview of the state of repository infrastructure, PID adoption and awareness in sub-Saharan Africa. Although there are some countries in the region with growing awareness of PIDs and growing adoption based on comparison carried out on the repository infrastructure and PID use in the region, the overall infrastructure is still nascent in sub-Saharan Africa. At the moment, South Africa stands out by all indicators. Others that seem to be making progress in terms of repository infrastructure include Kenya, Nigeria, Ghana, Zimbabwe, Lesotho, Ethiopia, Senegal, Côte d'Ivoire, Tanzania and Uganda. The number of repositories in these countries are lower compared to South Africa. This study did not consider the number of research institutions compared to the number of repositories in this region. Therefore, it may not be possible to compare the penetration of the infrastructure relative to the number of institutions in the countries within the region.

In terms of awareness, the report from UNESCO and COAR indicated the gap in PID awareness in the region. Certain parameters might have changed by the time of this publication, yet, the awareness could still be considered as low. The number of open access policies per country as seen in COAR data points to the lower awareness of PIDs in the region. A further comparison between the awareness and the available infrastructure per country still shows that there is still low penetration of PIDs as well as the awareness in the region. Although the repository infrastructure is still low in the region as evident in the data taken from OpenDOAR, ROAR and re3data, the uptake of PIDs is growing. Data taken from COAR shows a remarkable growth in the region between 2011 to 2019.

Although the region is making some progress, challenges persist. Resources are limited, including appropriate funding, knowledge and technology. These factors hinder widespread adoption. Although there are National Research and Educational Networks (NRENs) in the region, some countries lack the necessary technological infrastructure, connectivity, or expertise to implement and maintain PID systems effectively. Resources would be required to increase the awareness of PIDs in the region. This could be funding, human capacity development, awareness campaigns, direct engagements, collaborations from and within the continent to facilitate inter-governmental capacity building on the values and impacts of PIDs as well as direct support from stakeholders like service providers.

This landscape analysis indicates both progress and challenges in the adoption and implementation of PIDs in Africa. Continued efforts and collaborative initiatives are essential to further advance the use of PIDs, enhance research visibility, and facilitate greater global participation in African research endeavors. Ensuring the long-term sustainability of PID infrastructure in Africa requires ongoing support from governments, funding agencies, and international partners, along with the commitment of local stakeholders.

Engaging diverse stakeholders, including researchers, institutions, governments, funding bodies, and policymakers, remains crucial. Collaborative efforts are needed to establish best practices and standards tailored to the African context. Partnerships with global PID initiatives (like DataCite, ORCID, etc.) are essential for aligning African PID systems with international standards. This collaboration facilitates interoperability and ensures seamless integration with global research infrastructures. Establishing clear policies and governance structures around PIDs is essential. Policies that mandate or incentivize the use of PIDs in research outputs can significantly drive adoption. Investing in capacity building and training programs is critical to empower researchers and institutions with the knowledge and skills necessary to implement and utilize PIDs effectively.

It is recommended that future developments focus on integrating PIDs more deeply into the research ecosystem, expanding their use beyond publications to datasets, software, and other research outputs. Strengthening regional collaborations within Africa can also bolster PID implementation and adoption. It is suggested that further research be done using direct data collection from various countries in this region to compare the awareness of PIDs in the region to what is described in this report

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